

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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Showcasing best practices – part 1: “Recipes of Innovation – An EC2U Cookbook”

Report

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D5.5 Showcasing best practices – part 1: “Recipes of Innovation – An EC2U Cookbook”

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I. Describing the “Recipes of Innovation”

A. Rationale

“Recipes of Innovation. An EC2U Cookbook” is the title of a future publication that is jointly prepared by the RI4C2 partners of the EC2U Alliance. The publication will showcase best practices from the partners as well as offer informative and inspiring views on the topic of innovation. It should encourage students and researchers to gather the courage and knowledge to become innovators and connect ideas from the world of science to everyday life applications. In addition, the publication is a mean to make the innovation support structures and the Lighthouses of Innovation more visible. Target group of the publication are all students and researchers within the EC2U alliance and beyond, other Lighthouses of Innovation as well as the governance bodies of the EC2U universities and interested citizens.

On the way to PEKE, the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem, the Recipes of Innovation are a first measure of collaborative co-creation.

Figure 1: Integration-activity chart, picturing the development towards a Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem.

To kick off the co-creation of the publication, two workshops were held. The previously identified EC2U Lighthouses of Innovation (see report on D5.3) and the Work Package 5 (WP5) Board Members discussed on what it takes to be innovative and shared their best practices. The original plan to hold the workshops during an EC2U Forum could not be realized due to incompatible timelines between the main events of the EC2U Erasmus+ project (i.e. EC2U Forum with RI4C2 sessions) and the RI4C2 H2020 project. Instead, the workshop was organized as two virtual and interactive events (20 and 27/06/2022). A summarizing video of the sessions was uploaded onto the EC2U website.

B. Workshops

During the two workshops in June 2022, 16 participants joined in. A virtual collaborative tool (conceptboard) was used: this choice enabled the number of participants to increase after the workshop when additional partners added ideas to the conceptboard.

1. List of participants

20 June 2022	27 June 2022
Adina Mocanu	Adriana Zait
Costanza Baldrighi	Catarina Cunha Santos
Dana Strauß	Chabela de la Torre
Eleonore Roderfeld	Dana Strauß
Hendrik Eijsberg	David Zakoth
Lenuta Alboaic	Eleonore Roderfeld
Lina Diana	Hendrik Eijsberg
Ricardo Costa	Jorge Hernández
Rita Martins	Marjo Pihlavisto
	Oliver Pänke
	Pauli Ollikka
	Ricardo Costa
	Rita Martins

2. Questions & Method

Four key questions structured the workshop:

- What is innovation for you?
- Let's cook some innovation
 - Ingredients: What are the 3 top ingredients for successful innovation?
 - Hungry guests: Who are your customers?
 - The kitchen and the procedure: Which appliances do you need to transform the ingredients (ideas) into tasty meals (applicable products, services, goods)?

These four questions were addressed during open brainstorming and discussion rounds as well as phases of silent individual writing.

II. Results

The following screenshots show the results on conceptboard. The colors of the sticky notes identify the sessions: light yellow sticky notes were used in session 1 on 20 June, warm yellow was used in session 2 on 27 June, and orange was used for later individual additions.

For the full conceptboard visit: <https://app.conceptboard.com/board/6zmf-6xg9-esmf-g3sn-i34e>

Figure 2: Overview of the workshops' conceptboard

A. What is innovation for you?

Summary: While participants agreed that “**innovation is about doing something new and changing the status quo**”, they also agreed that it is a “**fuzzy process**”. The question arose “**if and how universities can connect (and foster?) (marketable) innovation with their social responsibility in order to create a benefit to society**”.

Input on conceptboard:

<p>Is innovation necessarily ground-breaking ?</p> <p>If innovation is too "great" (ex Deeptech) it is harder to market the change.</p> <p>More modest and simple innovation is easier to market. It is also easier to explain it and therefore gather the necessary support (funding, for instance)</p>	<p>The most ambitious innovation projects (ex Deeptech) aren't always targeted at an existing need.</p> <p>You can't therefore always define innovation as answering a need/problem</p>
<p>Innovation may require the early support of a private/industrial/economic partner.</p> <p>Some innovation may be or become inapplicable in practice if they aren't connected, early enough, with the needs and means of the market partners.</p>	<p>Innovativeness is a trait that some researchers have and others don't. It's cultural, it can be taught.</p> <p>This culture can be acquired by meaningful exchanges with partners.</p>
<p>Innovation isn't limited to high profile, quick success transfers to the market.</p> <p>Long term innovation project are less famous/supported - perhaps because they are less flashy ?</p> <p>The financial aspect is the driver here : some investors want a rapid return on investment.</p>	<p>At least in France, we focus overly much on engineering/hard science innovation.</p> <p>We don't enough of innovation in the social sciences.</p> <p>It stems from a link between innovation and economic gain. Not all innovation generates economic profit.</p>
<p>Social responsibility of universities : how do we connect that with innovation ?</p> <p>Researchers consider that innovation is something that brings meaningful change. It can be ground breaking or something that improves an existing product/system/situation</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Creating new ideas that are brought to the market. + Combining existing ideas in a new way + transfer research into a product/service + fuzzy process (at the beginning) with uncertain outcome 	<p>Innovation is "creative destruction". It's something that changes the way the things were being done</p>	<p>promoting the transition to a better world</p>
<p>bringing research results into application and into markets</p>	<p>creating a benefit for the society</p>	<p>Changing the status quo</p>
<p>Create (different) solutions for "old" problems</p>	<p>Inspiration to change</p>	<p>Doing things differently and making an impact</p>
<p>An Idea that has a market need and adds value</p>	<p>creating "new" needs and solutions to tackle them</p>	<p>very broad, can be invention or the process if you have something to improve. also your work can have innovation if we improve our processes.</p>
	<p>Inventing something that we didn't know we needed</p>	<p>doing something for the first time</p>

no one way to do it - national approaches might be different but then again some might be the same

how to get people (researchers) to become innovators?

ingredients might be the same - results might be different

Context is an important point for innovation:
- previous experiences and collaborations (good relationships with industry)
- research - from theoretical level to practical level
- economical environment

High quality of research is a prerequisite

crossing and pushing borders (and boundaries)

Innovation is the successful market exploitation of novel ideas, concepts, research results. The concept of innovation on Universities is diluted because they do not generally sell products, they need external cooperation --> Third Mission (universities have to collaborate to create impact)

Why do we Innovate ?

All researchers "innovate" : they create new knowledge. But is all scientific production "innovative" ?

One could say that not all scientific production answers existing questions. Some production just gives a new answer to an old question. The answer is not always helpful.

Could we define innovation as scientific production that is :
novel
has impact
addresses an unanswered need/question

Therefore, we innovate to adress unanswered questions

finding new questions to answer

add value

universities have a social responsibility to innovate

If universities do not equip their graduates with skills required to face the societal and economic issues of their time, those students will not find employment, no one will want to join that university, ... the university will perish

Therefore, it is crucial for universities to link research and teaching : research innovation will generate pertinent competences for citizens and the workforce

linked to societal causes
sustainability/mission of university

B. Ingredients for innovation

What are the 3 top ingredients for successful innovation?

Summary: The participants identified “time”, “network” and a “diverse team with a shared vision” as key ingredients. Nevertheless, they also pointed out that “(sharing) experience” is important. “Being open to (communicate about) failure” should be also normalized as part of the process.

Input on conceptboard:

C. Hungry guests: Who are your customers?

Summary: The Lighthouses of Innovation have different customers or direct “target groups”: **from local and regional governing bodies, entrepreneurial minded students to funding/regulatory bodies or investing partners.** Moreover, the participants emphasized that “**society in general is also (indirect) customer**” as innovators often address challenges that impact the DNA of everyday life.

Input on conceptboard:

D. The kitchen and the procedure

Which appliances do you need to transform the ingredients (ideas) into tasty meals (applicable products, services, goods)?

Summary: The participants listed a variety of concrete measures like “**reserve funding for proof-of-concept studies**” and include “**feedback from users/customers**” (“food tests”) on prototypes from the start. Also, to “**hire team members beside the core research team**” (“expert spice makers” is of vital important (project assistance, Tech-Transfer office etc.). Playing with the cooking metaphor the participants also added that a “**cellar**” where you store your ideas is of advantage as is a “**fridge whiteboard**” to keep your plans and proceedings transparent for everyone in your team.

Input on conceptboard:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + cooking team (Innovation creators) + well equipped kitchen (spices, pans etc.) + clear, simple but flexible menu (project plan) + test eaters: (to provide early feedback) + paying customers 		Highly qualified human resources in technology transfer
fast but individual processes	Resources and time to deepen the taste	Training and awareness of researchers to do so
resources and appropriate infrastructure (e.g. co-working, maker lab, incubator, accelerator, networks...)	A cellar! Where you store your cheese (innovative ideas that need an application) and wine (ideas that need to mature first) until they are ready	Ideas, results and solutions for urgent problems
A fridge whiteboard Where you list what innovations you have in your fridge, what ingredients are ready to be used/added, what innovations you are currently working on. So everyone in the kitchen knows what's going on	feedback from customers	Prototypes to reduce uncertainty when creating new products
funding for proofs-of-concept	An innovation foodie TV/radio show to listen to while you innovate in your kitchen It gives you ideas for your own innovation recipes	Funding for proof-of-concept studies

III. Summarizing video

In August 2022, a short video was produced to present the process and the results of the two workshop sessions. It shows the work on each question with key audio quotes. Rather than a real-time recording of several hours, the short video can attract a larger audience and highlight some of the most interesting insights of the workshop.

<https://ec2u.eu/lighthouses-of-innovation/>

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